

Investigation of new indirect spectrophotometric method for the determination of dichlorvos in environmental and agricultural samples

R. S. Dhundhel^a, M. K. Rai^{a*}, V. K. Gupta^a, E. K. Janghel^b and J. K. Rai^b

^aSchool of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010, Chhattisgarh, India

^bChhattisgarh Council of Science & Technology, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University Campus, Raipur-492 010, Chhattisgarh, India

E-mail : eteshkumar@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 19 May 2006, revised 28 August 2006, accepted 4 September 2006

Abstract : A new and highly sensitive spectrophotometric method is developed for the determination of sub ppm levels of widely used organophosphorus insecticide dichlorvos. The method is based on alkaline hydrolysis of dichlorvos to dichloroacetaldehyde, which react with *p*-aminoacetophenone in alkaline medium. The absorption maxima of the yellowish-orange compound formed is measured at 450 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range of 5.3 to 42 μg in a final solution volume of 25 ml (0.21–1.68 ppm). The lower limit of detection is 0.06 ppm. The molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and correlation coefficient were found to be $2.3 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $0.011 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and 0.9989 respectively. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.004 and 2.70% respectively. The method is simple, sensitive and free from interferences of other pesticides and diverse ions. Other organophosphorous pesticides do not interfere with the proposed method. The method has been satisfactorily applied to the determination of dichlorvos in environmental and agricultural samples.

Keywords : Dichlorvos, organophosphorus.

Dichlorvos [DDVP, Apavap, Vapona, Benfos] an organophosphorus insecticide, is highly toxic to mammals and human beings. It is readily absorbed through the skin, because it is volatile¹. A number of method have been described for the detection/determination of dichlorvos². Here a simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method is described for the determination of dichlorvos, where dichlorvos is hydrolysed to give dichloroacetaldehyde, which is further reacted with *p*-aminoacetophenone to produce a yellowish-orange compound with maximum absorbance at 450 nm (Scheme 1). The reagent is selective for dichlorvos, amongst the organophosphorus group. The colour system obeys Beer's law in the range of 0.21–1.68 ppm of dichlorvos. The method has been applied to the determination of dichlorvos in various samples of polluted water, vegetables, soil, foliages and environmental samples.

Results and discussion

Spectral characteristics : The yellowish-orange compound formed in the proposed reaction shows maximum absorption at 450 nm. All spectral measurements were carried out against deionised water as the reagent blank

showed negligible absorption at this wavelength. The colour system obeys Beer's law in the range of 5.3 to 42 μg of dichlorvos in 25 ml of final solution at 450 nm. The molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and correlation coefficient were found to be $2.3 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $0.011 \mu\text{g}$ and 0.9989 cm^{-2} , respectively.

Hydrolysis of dichlorvos to dichloroacetaldehyde was studied at different temperatures and alkalinity. It was observed that alkaline conditions were required for the hydrolysis. Hydrolysis of dichlorvos to dichloroacetaldehyde was studied with different molar concentration of sodium hydroxide (Fig. 1). Maximum hydrolysis was ob-

Fig. 1. Hydrolysis curve.

Note

Determination of dichlorvos in environmental and agricultural samples

The colour reaction involves the following steps.

- (1) Hydrolysis of dichlorvos to its corresponding aldehyde.
- (2) Reaction of aldehyde with *p*-aminoacetophenone under alkaline condition to form yellowish-orange compound, at 450 nm.

Scheme 1. Proposed reaction for formation of coloured species.

served with 1 ml of 1.0 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide at temperature of 30 °C as it gave maximum absorbance values, good stability and quantitative results. It was observed that above and below these concentration the absorbance value decreases and 1 ml of 0.05% *p*-aminoacetophenone was sufficient for complete colour reaction.

Precision of the method was checked by the replicate analysis of working standard solution containing 10 µg ml⁻¹ of dichlorvos in 25 ml final solution over a period of 7 days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ±0.004 and 2.70% respectively.

Effect of foreign species : The effect of common foreign species and pesticides were studied to assess the validity of the method. Known amounts of foreign species like common solvent such as benzene, ether and chloroform and pesticides were added to the standard solution containing 10 µg of dichlorvos prior to hydrolysis

Table 1. Effect of various pesticides and pollutants (concentration of dichlorvos 10 µg in 25 ml)

Foreign species	Tolerance limit ^a (ppm)	Foreign species	Tolerance limit ^a (ppm)
BHC, DDT	600	SO ₄ ²⁻	450
Benzene, ether	500	CO ₃ ²⁻	300
Malathion	400	NO ₂ ⁻	150
2:4-D, 2:4:5-T	350	NO ₃ ⁻	100
Cyanide	200	Cu ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺	60
Kelthane, fluoride, chloroform	100	Sb ³⁺	50
Parathion	50	Ca ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺	40
		K ⁺ , Cl ⁻	30

^aThe amount causing an error of ±2% in absorbance value.

BHC = Benzene hex chloride, DDT = dichlorodiphenyl trichloroethane. 2:4-D = (2,4-Dichlorophenoxy)acetic acid, 2:4:5-T = (2,4,5-trichlorophenoxy)acetic acid.

and the solution was analysed by the proposed method. The method was found to be free from interferences of most of the foreign species and pesticides (Table 1).

Experimental

A Systronics UV-Vis spectrophotometric model 104 and a Systronic pH meter model 335 was used for pH measurements. A Remi C-854/4 clinical centrifuge force of 1850 g with fixed swingout rotors was used for centrifugation. All reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Double-distilled deionised water was used throughout. Dichlorvos (Hindustion Ciba-Geigy Bombay, India). A stock solution of 1 mg ml⁻¹ was prepared in ethanol. Working standard solution were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock standard solution with ethanol. *p*-Aminoacetophenone (E. Merck, Germany) : 0.05% (m/v) solution of the reagent was prepared by dissolving 0.05 g of *p*-aminoacetophenone in 100 ml ethanol.

Procedure : An aliquot of the test solution containing 5.3 to 42 µg of dichlorvos was taken in a 25 ml graduated tube and to it, 1.0 ml of 1.0 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide was added. The solution was kept for 15 min at room temperature for complete hydrolysis. 1 ml of *p*-aminoacetophenone was added, shaken thoroughly and pH was adjusted to 9.0–9.3. The solution was kept for 25 min for full colour development. The solution was then diluted to the mark with water and absorbance was measured at 450 nm against a reagent blank.

Determination of dichlorvos in water : River water samples, receiving run off water from agricultural fields, sprayed with dichlorvos were collected. These samples were extracted with 2 × 25 ml portions of diethyl ether. Ether solution was evaporated to dryness and residue was dissolved in 50 ml of ethanol. Aliquots were then analysed as described above.

Determination of dichlorvos in soil and vegetables : Various samples such as soil, cauliflower and tomato were collected from the fields, dichlorvos was used as an insecticide. The samples were weighed (50 g) crushed and extracted with 2 × 25 ml portions of diethyl ether. Di-

ethyl ether was then evaporated to dryness and residue was dissolved in 50 ml of ethanol. Aliquots were then analysed as described above.

The proposed method has been applied satisfactorily to the determination of dichlorvos in various samples of water, vegetables, and soil before extraction with ether. The results are in a good agreement with the reported method².

To check the recoveries (10 µg of dichlorvos in 25 ml), known amount of dichlorvos were added to these samples and then analysed by the proposed as well as the reported method. The recoveries were found to be 88 to 99%.

Conclusion : The advantage of the proposed method is mainly its sensitivity, simplicity and selectivity and higher stability of the coloured solution. The proposed method has been successfully applied for the determination of dichlorvos in water, soil and vegetables.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the Head, School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur and Director General, Chhattisgarh Council of Science & Technology for providing laboratory and grant facilities.

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